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KANSEI EVALUATION OF JEWELRY'S SHININESS

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ABSTRACT

In this research, we focus on first, how people feel when they see jewelry. Second, how people feel when jewelry have different degree of shininess. Feelings are described as the Japanese word, *Kansei*, and which are collected from interviews with employees of jewelry shops and general public.

For this research, four images of silver rings are used as stimuli and the experiment is conducted by Semantic Differential Method. We tried to reproduce the shininess of rings in some ways. With these images of rings, we attempted to explore how shininess affects feelings.

Throughout the course of the experiment, we received comments from participants. Mostly, the comments concerned images of stimuli and the method of experiment. Results of the study revealed, differences between genders and rings, but it was not significant. However, the strongest shininess has its own unique curve.

We also found some characteristics of feelings of shininess by the *Kansei* evaluation through Semantic Differential Method, but more research is needed to find other factors.

Keywords: Shininess, Metal, Jewelry

INTRODUCTION

When people buy jewelry they take into consideration many factors such as brand, price, design, color of stone, and meaning of jewelry. Jeon Yee[1], in her doctoral thesis on the Relationship between the Types of Consumer's Ornament-Wearing Motives and Choice Behavior, divided the factors of ornament-wearing motives through

ethnographic study. As a result, 7 factors were extracted such as aesthetic, incantation, hedonic, conspicuous, self-expressive, physiological, and social motives. Although the motives of the people who wear the ornaments were investigated, the affection of physical properties of jewelry is not well understood. In a jewelry shop, shiny metal objects attract people's attention first. Shininess is one of metal's unique properties which have strong visual and psychological effects when it is used in jewelry. Shininess cannot be described as Saturation, Hue, and Brightness. For this reason, jewelry designers attach metal samples on design sheets with their sketch. By attaching metal samples or particles of metal, designers do not have to worry about misunderstandings during product lines. However, how do Jewelry designers know how to choose the right color for customers? The colors reflecting the designer's feelings are not in accordance with those of the consumers. In addition, though the growth of plating technology has improved, the diversity of jewelry field, there are not many studies which focus on metal colors and degree of shininess in jewelry. These problems make designers hesitate when they decide the color and shininess of metal.

In this context, this research investigates *Kansei* Evaluation of Jewelry's shininess through describing feelings with *Kansei* words. Our experiment explores evaluating between feelings and shininess, and creating objective images of Shininess.

This study is an opportunity to understand customer's behavior and to develop new designs and marketing techniques around jewelry. Our research also connects to a high end product that could be discussed in a quantitative way.

HYPOTHESIS

It is assumed that the physical properties of shininess affect people's minds. The hypothesis could be as following; when jewelry has different shiny degrees in one material in same ring, they create different *Kansei* in the human mind.

METHOD

Based on the above hypothesis, experiments were conducted to investigate *Kansei* produced by seeing objects which have different degrees of shininess. For *Kansei* evaluation, Semantic Differential Method is used. [2] In order to analyze and verify this hypothesis, silver has been chosen because of its high reflection degree and its common use which makes it familiar for the general public [3].

For each ring, the subjects must choose the levels in the scales of 14 *Kansei* words to describe it. These words have been collected thanks to a former survey conducted among employees of jewelry shops in Ginza and Shinjuku.

SUBJECTS

In this experiment, the participants were 15 males and 15 females aged 18 to 29. The participants were students and researchers in University of Tsukuba and Tokyo city. All female participants had some experience buying jewelry, whereas men have less experience and knowledge about jewelry. However, in recent days, the numbers of consumers of jewelry and accessories have increased not only in women but also men. [4]

STIMULI

CREATING THE IMAGES

Figure 1 shows an example of metal rings which have various colors and different degrees of shininess.

colors of metal		Yellow	White	Red	Black
degree of shininess	Strong				
	Soft				

Figure 1. 4 groups of metal colors

Each color represents materials. (Yellow: gold, brass, and copper/White: silver, platinum, stainless steel, aluminum, chrome, steel /Red: bronze, pink-gold /Black: gun-metal) Despite classifying the color of metal, it is difficult to distinguish to the borders of the rings, due to the similarity of color in groups of White and Black, and the diversity of metal alloys.

Figure 2 shows an example of three-dimensional images of rings which are created by 3D design software-Rhinoceros. In all images, the ring on the left is polished silver plain and the ring on the right is chrome satin plain. In both rings, the base color is R247 G247 B247, and the ground plane is aluminum satin which is brushed heavily. Although these three images have different reflections, the participants commented that the rings look far from real jewelry and seem to be "3D images". In addition, they mentioned that it is hard to see the shininess of the rings through the images.

Figure 2. Rings created by 3D design software

For these reasons, four new silver rings are shown to the participants as stimuli. Figure3 shows the different degrees of shininess of the rings. The images have been created by Photoshop software as 2D images, and are produced by on-paper survey. According to the characteristics of metal mirrors, we chose silver as stimuli. The silver of both plated and solid mirrors which were polished to the best obtainable brightness without regard to optical flatness, shows high reflectance. [5]

Furthermore, these rings do not bring up the image of particular brand's product with their simple shape to the participants.

Figure 3. Images of Rings as stimuli

Ring1 Ring2 Ring3 Ring4

COLLECTING KANSEI WORDS

In order to collect *Kansei* words, we visited four shops (two wedding jewelry shops, one silver accessory shop and one made-to-order jewelry shop) in Shinjuku and Ginza. (Fig4) We asked the staff “What words do you use when you talk with customers in shop?” They gave abundant vocabulary more than the general public. Since the staffs were often in contact with customers for their business, they did not only explain the items but they also expressed feelings and images of appearance when the jewelry is worn on one’s finger or neck.

Also, words were added from shopping channels on TV, magazines, catalogues. Figure 5 shows fourteen words that are used the most. Additionally, we gathered other words and expressions as follows; (jewelry) match one’s look, easy to wear, feels good to wear, practical, casual, fun, delicate design, stylish, noble, luxury, fashionable, and a feature of material.

Figure 4. Shops for interviews

RESULT

The results show that there are differences in genders. (fig5) In the subdued-glittering scale, the females distinguished different degrees of shininess in every rings, but the males felt that no differences in the rings. The tendency is also shown in the boring-attractive scale. Interestingly, even though

Figure 5. Differences in Genders

the results show that each ring has different degrees of shininess, both females and males feel all rings are “little beautiful” except for Ring4. Also we can see the evaluation of each ring in Figure6. The curves of Ring1, Ring2, and Ring3 are similar; however Ring4 has its own unique curve.

The curve of Ring4 shows differences from the other rings in simple-gorgeous, boring-attractive, subdued-glitter, quiet-showy, unfriendly-friendly, ordinary-gorgeous, general-character scale. Both female and male’s curves of Ring4 are close to the right, meaning they have positive images.

DISCUSSION

Through our experiment, we discovered that women and men show different *Kansei* evaluations with silver rings and their degrees of shininess; Women prefer stronger shininess than soft shininess, whereas men show little differences within the rings. Both females and males evaluated Ring1 to Ring3 as “pretty general”. The participants commented that simplicity and no-stone design of the rings affected the evaluation. They also mentioned sweet or lovely feelings are related with shape and motif of the rings. This research is a work in progress which plans to provide the actual object to subjects in future work. Moreover, certain definitions of words and profile information of participants are inquired.

Figure 6. Differences in Rings

DEFINITION OF WORDS

Through this study, we found problems with the definition of the word shininess, which is imperfectly understood by the participants. There are many words related to light and metal as follows; gloss, glitter, reflection, mirrored color, luster, luminosity, glow, metallic luster, metallic frost, polished surface, diffuse reflection, optical reflectivity, specular reflectance, and specular gloss. To prevent confusion of metal’s properties, proper words should be considered in future work.

SUGGESTION ON BETTER STIMULI

After the experiments, most of the participants commented that it was hard to distinguish “strong” and “soft” shininess. Furthermore, it was hard to recognize the differences between Ring1 and Ring2, Ring2 and Ring3. However, participants had no difficulty of Ring4.

To obtain an accurate evaluation, the actual object is possible as stimuli. Participants can see, touch, and wear real jewelry on their body, which it will help them to evaluate their feelings.

Making the actual jewelry should be conducted cautiously, because they are accompanied with some problems; gold and silver can leave traces on the skin in some instances due to a mild chemical reaction between the metal and the skin on wearer,

despite the metal being 100% nickel-free. If participants have an allergic reaction to metal, the experiment should be stopped immediately.

In addition, Jewelry plated with genuine silver and gold oxidize over time, meaning the degree of shininess and color of metal is not in stable condition.

PROFILE INFORMATION

In the experiment, the profile information of participants; sex and age, were added to introduce more information to their profile. For example, monthly expenses of jewelry, occupation, social class, the number of items people have, personal preference of color, stone, metal, items etc.

MEASUREMENT OF SHININESS

In chromatics, metals such as gold and silver are difficult to determine as RGB or CMYK on paper or computer screen. Therefore, CIE (Commission International d’Eclairage) suggests a method of reflection measurement in the guidelines. Recently, some of the measurement machines are being developed such as REFO® 60D (Dr. lange), Mirror-TYI-gloss (BYK-Gardner).

CONCLUSION

The characteristics of evaluation of shininess revealed that females have a tendency to evaluate shininess more sensitively than males. Also, we found

that strong shininess has an effect on evaluation which has different characters. In particular, Ring4 is more attractive, feminine, and gorgeous, but less friendly and not as lovely as other rings. However, our research requires additional factors about jewelry and customers.

Furthermore, we recognize that providing high quality stimuli which is easy to distinguish for participants, is an important progress.

FUTURE WORKS

In future works, we will investigate the interrelationship between participant's personality and shininess.

According to Georg Simmel-German sociologist, philosopher, and critic-interprets, jewelry enhances or extends the idea of personality, as it were as an emanation of their acts. He also mentioned that people decorate for themselves and it is possible when people decorate for others.

In addition, he points out that the rays of the jewelry, which is the sensual attention that attracts people, create the personality of such an expansion or intensification of its sphere. This is especially pronounced when jewelry decorated. [6]

To see how jewelry's shininess affects people's *Kansei*, we decided to investigate the personality of both jewelry wearers and others who watch wearers.

In the step of collecting *Kansei* words, we found that people tend to use words describing the appearance of a person who wears jewelry, more than explaining jewelry items. In this research, the words describing a person wearing jewelry were 25 words, whereas the words explaining jewelry items were 15 words. For instance, the most used words by both the general public and salespersons were 'It (jewelry) suits you/me', and 'It (jewelry) makes me look beautifully (adjective such as cute, elegance, cool)'.

As the result of the research, we assume that the personality of participants is an essential prerequisite for investigating how jewelry's shininess affects people.

For this research, we considered to employ Maudsley Personality Inventory (MPI) of H.J.Eysenck or the Schwartz Value Survey as the first step of future work.

In the step of evaluation of subject's *Kansei*, we will ask participants to chose and wear the jewelry they evaluate. The act of "decorating body" is a distinctive difference between jewelry and other products.

For this evaluation step, contracting simple shape from other items such as necklace, bracelet, and earrings will be need; In future work, we expect to assess the interrelationship between shininess and personality.

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